

A Study of Competitive and Consecutive Second Order Reactions: N—Alkylation of Amines by Alkyl Iodides*—Part II

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The kinetics of alkylation of primary, secondary and tertiary aromatic amines with methyl iodide and ethyl iodide in pure nitrobenzene medium is reported. Frost-Schwemer treatment of two step consecutive second order reactions has been utilized for the separation of rate constants in reactions with primary aromatic amines. The results are discussed in the light of basicity, nucleophilicity, electronic and steric effects.

In our previous communication¹ we have presented evidences that alkylation is stopping at the tertiary stage for the primary aromatic amines with methyl iodide. The reaction has now been thoroughly investigated for all substituted anilines with methyl and ethyl iodide in pure nitrobenzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solvents and all the compounds, except methyl and ethyl iodides, used were purified as described earlier (*loc. cit.*). The boiling points at atmospheric pressure and refractive indices for the compounds determined for the sodium line at 20° were; nitrobenzene 210°, n_D 1.5524, aniline 183°, n_D 1.5863, *N*-methyl aniline 193°, n_D 1.5702, dimethyl aniline 193°, n_D 1.5587, *p*-toluidine 45°†; *m*-toluidine 199°, n_D 1.5771; *o*-toluidine 197°, n_D 1.5728; *p*-chloroaniline 70°†; *m*-chloroaniline 230°, n_D 1.5931; *o*-chloroaniline 207°, n_D 1.5895; *m*-bromoaniline 251°, n_D 1.6260 and β -naphthylamine 111°†.

Rate measurements : For fast reactions flasks containing the stock solutions were allowed to come to bath temperature. Insulated pipettes maintained at bath temperature were used to remove and transfer 50 ml aliquots to the reaction flask. The reaction flask was painted black to prevent exposure to light and it was fitted with narrow neck which just admitted the pipettes. At the intervals of time ranging from half an hour to two hr. a 5 ml sample of the reaction mixture was withdrawn, discharged into 10 ml of cold silver nitrate and immediately titrated with standard potassium thiocyanate using ferric alum indicator. For the slower reactions it was necessary to modify the procedure by utilising thin walled ampoules. The reaction mixture was prepared at 25° and nine aliquots of 10 ml were placed into ampoules. These were cooled, sealed and placed in the constant temperature bath. At intervals of time ranging from five hours to two days the ampoules were crushed in 20 ml of silver nitrate and the free silver nitrate was titrated as before. All the expansion corrections due to high temperature have been taken into account in calculation. The experiments had been repeated for all the runs and the results agreed within $\pm 3\%$. By

* The paper appeared in *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, (5), 430 should be deemed as Part-I.

1. P. S. R. Murti and G. P. Panigrahi, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, (5), 430.

† Melting points; Methyl and ethyl iodides were of Riedel (pure).

independent runs it has been checked that there is no reaction between CH_3I and AgNO_3 under these conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rate constants for all substituted anilines with methyl iodide are given below :

TABLE I

Second order rate constants ($\times 10^3$ l. moles $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$) for reaction of bases with methyl iodide at 80° in nitrobenzene

Bases	k_1^*	k_1^\dagger	k_2	k_1^\dagger/k_2
Aniline	55.37	55.29	6.50	—
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	155.60	167.9	10.23	15.21
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	97.00	96.00	8.92	10.87
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	30.68	30.36	2.78	11.00
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	18.50	19.55	15.25	1.21
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	8.70	9.39	5.12	1.70
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	3.47	3.65	3.47	1.00
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline	10.90	11.61	3.00	—
B-Naphthylamine	54.29	55.06	8.831	—

* Computed by Frost-Schwemer treatment.

† Initial rate constants upto 20% of the reaction calculated using second order rate expression.

The separation of rate constants has been done by using Frost-Schwemer treatment^{2a,2b}. Reactions are clear second order consecutive reactions stopping at the tertiary stage. The initial rate constants are compared with the rate constants of the first step in all the cases to show the accuracy of the Frost-Schwemer treatment.

Generally many equilibria are suggested for the alkylation of primary aromatic amines and secondary aromatic amines, such as the ionization of the halide, interaction of the monoalkyl onium salt with the free amine and the reversible decomposition of the monoalkylonium salt to yield the free amine and methyl iodide. We have already reported (*loc. cit.*) that the alkylation is a two step process with primary aromatic amines and a one step process with secondary aromatic amines indicating that the reactions are stopping at the tertiary stage because of the stabilization of the dialkyl aryl onium cation by hyperconjugative interaction. The work of Saul Patai and Weiss³ with diphenyl amine and methyl iodide in dimethyl formamide supports our conclusion that monoalkylation is occurring in secondary aromatic amines following a simple second order kinetics as against the usual classical idea that the reaction is complicated with several equilibria. The kinetic data presented here confirm our earlier finding that the reactions of primary aromatic amines are essentially

2a. A. Frost and W. C. Schwemer; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73** 4541.

2b. A. Frost and W. C. Schwemer; *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 1262.

3. Saul Patai and S. Weiss; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1035.

two step consecutive second order reactions in this medium with the other equilibria being of not much significance. The above arguments find support also from the work of Brown⁴ on ortho-phenylene-diamine with methyl-iodide. It is postulated by Brown that *o*-phenylene diamine reacts in 1 : 1 stoichiometry and yields

cation which is stable and hence no further alkylation is occurring even though it is a primary aromatic amine. It appears that the stability of the cation is responsible for no further reaction. Our argument is that alkylation stops if the cation is stabilized seems substantiated by the above work also.

The relative reactivity shows all toluidines are reacting faster than aniline quite in consonance with their *pK_a* values except the ortho toluidine which is reacting slow as there is steric retardation. It is also seen that all the chloro anilines are reacting slower than aniline indicating that what is rate controlling in these alkylation reactions is bond formation between substrate and base. Electron releasing substituents in the base are accelerating the reaction. All these comments apply easily to the first step of alkylation which is as follows :—

But as regards the second stage of alkylation the reaction is a combination of two factors, (1) decomposition of the protonated species, (2) further alkylation.

4. H. C. Brown and K. L. Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 24.

Hence it is easily seen that electron withdrawing substituents in the base allow the protonated species to breakdown easily and allow further alkylation to take place whereas electron releasing substituents in the base stabilize the protonated species making the decomposition of the species difficult which results in the second stage of alkylation becoming slow. A look into the ratios k_1/k_2 (Table I) of toluidines and chloro-anilines will make this point clear.

The trend indicates that the second stage of alkylation tends to be faster for chloro-anilines compared to the second stage of alkylation for toluidines.

A plot of $\log k_1$ vs σ and σ^+ shows linearity. Similarly a plot of $\log k_1$ vs pK_a shows fair linearity. We have also plotted $\log k_1$ vs nucleophilicity ' n ' computed by us⁵ for these bases in their reactions with benzyl chloride. This shows much better linearity showing nucleophilicity is a better correlating measure.

TABLE II

Base	Nucleophilicity ' n '
Aniline	4.49
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	4.828
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	4.674
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	4.247
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	4.135
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	3.923
β -Naphthyl-amine	4.421

Variation in the structure of alkyl halide : The rate constants in the alkylation of various bases with ethyl-iodide are given below :

TABLE III

Base	<i>Solvent</i> : Nitrobenzene	
	$10^3 k_1$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Aniline	8.00*	2.00
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	19.9*	4.35
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	10.41	—
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	4.46	—
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	3.32	—
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	1.40	—
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	0.62	—

* values are those computed by F.S. treatment.

5. P. S. R. Murti and G. P. Panigrahi; Part III of the Proceedings of the 55th Session of Indian Science Congress, 1968, p. 152.

The table shows that there is a general decrease in the rate of reaction as the alkyl halide is varied from methyl to ethyl. The decrease in reactivity towards displacement reactions in the methyl, ethyl series was originally attributed by Huges and Ingold⁶ to the inductive effect of alkyl substituents. More recently those workers⁷ have proposed that half of the effect should be ascribed to a polar factor with the remainder attributed to steric interaction. On the other hand Evans⁸ ascribes the entire effect to steric interaction. The work of Brown^{9,10} also supports this conclusion. As indicated earlier in this two step alkylation process, the first step is slower with a much slower second step. In the case of aniline and *p*-Toluidine reactions could be followed up to sixty percent thus utilizing Frost-Schwemer treatment for the computation of the rate constants of both the steps. In other cases the reactions could not be followed with convenience upto sixty percent. But it is understood that even here two steps of alkylation are taking place leading to dialkyl aryl onium salt which is stable.

Reactions of N-methyl aniline and N- N-Dimethyl aniline with alkyl iodides :—

TABLE IV

Solvent : Nitrobenzene

Base	Temperature in °C	Substrate : CH ₃ I	Substrate : C ₂ H ₅ I
		10 ³ <i>k</i> in 1.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	10 ³ <i>k</i> in 1.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
N-Methylaniline	60	45.29	—
	70	74.02	—
	80	141.9	13.43
Dimethylaniline	60	42.93	—
	70	67.8	—
	80	116.08	2.67

Earlier we had pointed out that dimethyl-aniline (*loc. cit.*) is less reactive than N-Methylaniline, probably because of the steric contribution of bulky methyl groups in the former. The above table confirms our finding at a number of temperatures. The reactivity of dimethylaniline becomes much less when the methyl group in the alkyl iodide is replaced by an ethyl group which may be due to the presence of bulky groups both in the base as well as in the substrate. The plots of log *k* vs 1/*T* are linear for these reactions.

The energy of activation for N-Methylaniline methyl iodide reaction is about 14.20 K.cal/mole compared to 19.93 K.Cal/mole for the second step in the alkylation of aniline with CH₃I. (*loc. cit.*). This difference in the energy of activation can be attributed to the presence of a free base in the former whereas a protonated base has to react in the latter thus

6. E. D. Hughes and C. K. Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 245.
7. I. Dostrovsky, E. D. Hughes and C. K. Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 173; 1948, 1283.
8. A. G. Evans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1943, **42**, 719.
9. H. C. Brown, and N. R. Eldred, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 445.
10. H. C. Brown and A. Cahn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1715.

requiring higher energy of activation. The energy of activation for dimethylaniline—methyl-iodide reaction is 13.73 K.cal/mole in conformity with the requirements of bimolecular reactions.

TABLE V

Base	<i>E</i> (K.Cal/mole)	$\log_{10} P_z$	ΔH (K.Cal/mole)	ΔS (e.u.)
Aniline 1st step*	9.827*	3.05	9.12	-44.9
2nd step	19.93	8.37	19.22	-20.5
N-Methylaniline	14.19	5.40	13.48	-34.1
N.N.Dimethylaniline	13.73	5.78	13.02	-32.4

* Taken from Part I of this work.

The table of thermodynamic parameters makes it clear that the frequency factor, activation energy and enthalpy parallel each other. The small frequency factors would mean that the standard entropy of activation ' ΔS^\ddagger ' has relatively large negative value. The $\log_{10} PZ$ values being lower than the normal value of 11.3 might be due to any of the following factors :—

- (1) Endothermic formation of the complex prior to the reaction proper.
- (2) The necessity for the ionisation of either or both the reactants.
- (3) Deactivation by solvent molecules.
- (4) Stringent condition of orientation or of internal phase of the reacting molecules at the moment of impact, and
- (5) The existence of strong forces of repulsion.

There is a linear relationship between enthalpy of activation and entropy of activation.

Solvent Effect :

TABLE VI

Temperature 80°

Base	Substrate	Solvent	$10^3 k_1$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Aniline	CH ₃ I	Nitrobenzene 100%	55.37	6.50
Aniline	CH ₃ I	Nitrobenzene 80% (v/v) and Ethanol 20% (v/v)	134.70	—
Aniline	C ₂ H ₅ I	Nitrobenzene 100%	8.00	2.00
Aniline	C ₂ H ₅ I	Nitrobenzene 80% (v/v) and Ethanol 20% (v/v)	21.59	—

The reaction with methyl-iodide and ethyl-iodide has been extended to nitrobenzene—alcohol mixtures to study the effect of addition of a protic solvent to nitrobenzene. The results are interesting that there is an acceleration of the first step with both alkyl halides and there is large retardation for the second step. The Frost-Schwemer treatment could not be used as the later stages of the reaction were very slow making it difficult to follow the reaction up to 60%, a necessary condition for the application of Frost-Schwemer treatment. It is significant to remark that by using only second order rate expression perfect rate constants were obtained till 40% of the reaction indicating that the incursion of the second step is negligible it being much retarded in this solvent mixture.

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